

Changes in Hospital Healthcare and Nursing

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Introduction

The U.S. health system is a monster. This is by far the most expensive in the world. Currently, various changes are experienced by healthcare system of United States especially in nursing profession. Barack Obama Health Care Reform is the most significant change in the U.S. health care system since 1960 as a program was created Medicare, paid budget scheme that allows taking care of the health of those Americans, who passed for 65 years. Nursing is considered as the largest segment of healthcare workforce of a nation having approx 3 million members. Nurses are playing an important role and helping realize the aims and objectives set forth in Affordable Care Act of 2010. The Affordable Care Act has opened the door to the nursing profession. There are various barriers preventing nurses from being able to rapidly and effectively respond to evolving healthcare system and quickly changing settings of health care. Institute of Medicine (IOM) and the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation (RWJF) developed a report and took an initiative to respond to the transform nursing profession and overcome these barriers (D'Antonio, 2010). The report included various recommendations to transform the nursing profession for future effectiveness. In this paper I am going to evaluate these changes in healthcare system of US and shall analyze impact of these changes on nursing profession.

Changes in health care System of United States

In such a rapidly developing environment as health and social care, change is a constant feature just like it is in the everyday lives of the people. A critical analysis of the leader's role in managing change in the current Irish healthcare system is quite necessary in the present times. Nurses are facing some major challenges in this regard to adjust themselves in the current global economic crisis. All these factors indicate that nurses should play a vital role to bring a change in the healthcare system. It is not an easy task, but the nurses have ability in contributing their efforts for bringing change in the healthcare system. The activities that nurses can perform for bringing change in the healthcare system will be the major part of the topic. Therefore, all the issues related to the role of nursing in managing change will be discussed in detail.

Institute of Medicine issued this report was developed in October 2010, which aimed at bringing extraordinary change in the nursing profession of US health care. Following are some changes that IOM report tried to bring in US health care.

Change # 1

Under this recommendation IOM has tried to focus on two different but interlink subcategories. The first subcategory speaks of practice while the other pertains to nurse residency programs. It says that no matter a nurse working as an advanced practice nurse or as a staff nurse in the community, he/she should be able to practice to the full extent of their training and education. On the other hand it is very important to implement multilevel residency programs to the entrance of a nurse can be managed for example Student to practitioner.

Change # 2

This recommendation states that nurses should attain high level of training and education to promote seamless academic progression and this can be achieved when nursing education system would be effective and improved (www.theatlantic.com). Thus, the nursing education system should be improved so that quality care could be provided across the setting. Demands of healthcare system have increased and these can be met when nurses would be highly educated and trained. In other words, nurses should be educated with health professionals and physicians not only as a student but they should continue doing it throughout their career. Nurses daily deal with diverse population so the focus of their education and training should also be focusing on diverse education on various culture and ethnicity. It will not only improve relationship between patients and nurse but also quality of the care will be improved. This change calls for college levels of apprenticeship and training for nurses in advising that the next decade, 80 percent of nurses in the United States accept a bachelor's amount and, during this aforementioned period, acceleration the amount of professionals with doctoral degrees.

Change # 3

In order to promote and cultivate leaders within nursing precession, nurses should work with various health professionals and physicians. It will basically advance the profession of nursing and will prepare them effective skills required to provide quality care. Being full partner involves taking responsibility for identifying areas and problem of system waste, making important adjustments, devising and implementing improvement plans. Leadership related competencies should be embedded in order to make sure that nurses are ready to jump on to leadership roles (www.iom.edu). Furthermore mentoring and leadership development programs

should be provided to nurses at all levels and effective culture should be fostered to promote leadership values.

Change # 4

Under this recommendation again we can see two subcategories: one is effective planning while the other is policy planning. Healthcare system of United States can be transformed if the data related to healthcare workforce is accurately analyzed and collected (www.theatlantic.com). In order to bring changes in healthcare system of United States, especially related to nursing profession comprehensive data on types and number of health professionals is required which can only be achieved with effective workforce planning and policy making.

Implications

Health reform and the Institute of Medicine (IOM) Report on the future of nursing have been at the forefront of nursing. Nurse leaders today have already begun this important work of redesigning health for the people while preparing the next generation to continue the work. It has implicated somewhat positively to the nursing profession. With the help of these changes in US healthcare system, nurses are able to get proper education and training which has helped them in providing quality care and building effective patient and nurse relationship. Nurses also have started to serve as a conduit to the community to help the people understand and accept the new healthcare systems. Since most of the health disciplines, this will be a strong voice for improvements in patient care quality, cost and safety (Yergan. 2011). A more diverse population of the United States, which includes baby boomers and people of different racial and ethnic backgrounds, are also benefit from the diversity in the profession. When nurses are used to their

full capacity, it leads to better health in the American public. As today's nurses embrace its administration role that actively coact with added bloom disciplines in managing accommodating care. When all bloom professions embrace the abstraction that they are all professionals and anniversary conduct brings a different set of abilities and attributes of the table, interdisciplinary accord advance accommodating care. Today's leaders are committing to assistant our nursing advisers are arising leaders to ensure they accept the abilities all-important to accomplish in this rapidly alteration ambiance (Judd, 2012).

Conclusion

In conclusion we can say that changes brought to US healthcare system have positively impacted Nursing profession. These changes calls for effective workforce planning and policy, saying that such a goal can only be achieved through the collection of better data and a more efficient information infrastructure .This largest workforce should and can play an essential role in this transformation since healthcare system of United States have the potential and opportunity to transform. However the healthcare system of United States can not only be changed solely by nurses, support of current regulatory, government, business, insurance industries, and professional association is also important. If all these parties work together, they can ensure the effectiveness of healthcare system by providing affordable, seamless, and quality care that would be accessible to all and will result in effective health outcomes.

References

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